

IPBES VA Chapter 4 - Literature review for the Amazonia ILK case study / IPBES values assessment (4.10)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. A review was conducted to search for information about values and valuation of nature in multiple sources, and considering various types of knowledge, including indigenous and local knowledge (ILK), in the context of the Amazonia. In particular, undertaking a case study like this, proved to be an effective way of communicating the crucial role of values of nature in current and future decision-making and planning policy. This review was carried out following FPIC principles.

Process overview

miro

Protocol

A first set of academic and grey literature was obtained while preparing a search and analysis of information for *sections 4.4.2 and 4.6.5*¹ while further evidence was collected through the searches described below.

¹ See document (A) of the report of the Literature review on values considered in decision-making contexts at local level (10.5281/zenodo.4396271).

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search for relevant academic and grey literature
- **Search languages:** Abstract/Title in English
- **Sample extracted:** 40 documents

Details for academic literature search:

- **Search engine:** ScienceDirect
- **Exact search date:** April, 2020
- **Search terms:**

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Amazon conservation policies" OR "carbon market and local
    governance" OR "overlapped areas between protected areas and indigenous
    territories Amazon")
```

Details for grey literature search:

- **Search engine:** Google
- **Exact search date:** April, 2020
- **Search terms for finding grey literature:**

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY (decree, resolution, co-design, management, overlapped areas
    between Indigenous Authorities and National Parks)
```

Treatment applied: No databases were downloaded, but relevant documents were accessed directly. Abstracts and/or introductory paragraphs of the found documents were used to screen the results and select the relevant literature. Based on expert knowledge, relevant information from the 40 documents was recorded into a word processor, to then be used to inform the sections.

In September 2020, a general plan of activities was structured, and topics such as the ongoing COVID-19 pandemics and other relevant issues, such as “sustainability education” were included to search for further information.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search for relevant information to retrieve academic literature.
- **Search languages:** Abstract/Title in English
- **Search engine:** ScienceDirect, Scopus, Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** September, 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 168 documents

Search terms used:

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ('deforestation AND Amazonia' AND 'policies')
```

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ('Amazonia AND indigenous views')
```

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ('Amazonia Indigenous territories')
```

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ('deforestation AND COVID-19')
```

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ('deforestation AND coronavirus')
```

```
TS= (
```

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ('experiential AND learning' AND 'sustainability')
```

```
TS= (  
  TITLE-ABS-KEY ('sustainability education')
```

```
TS= (  
  TITLE-ABS-KEY ('learning AND communities' AND 'sustainability')
```

Treatment applied: No databases were downloaded, but relevant documents were accessed directly. Based on expert knowledge, a screening process was carried out by using abstracts to select relevant literature. Important information was recorded in a word processor to inform the case study.

In order to attend to the comments from the second external review of the values assessment (received in March 2021), further searches to retrieve academic papers and books were performed.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search for relevant information to retrieve academic literature.
- **Search languages:** Abstract/Title in English
- **Search engine:** ScienceDirect, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar
- **Exact search date:** May, 2021
- **Sample extracted:** 40 documents

Treatment applied: No databases were downloaded, but relevant documents were accessed directly. A screening process was carried out by using abstracts to select relevant literature, based on the following criteria (defined during the Third Author Meeting - April 2021): (1) a focus on more specific topics; (2) relevance regarding transformative change (as used in the assessment); and (3) publication in the decades following seminal studies.

From the processes of retrieval and selection of relevant documents obtained through the three searches, a total of 147 references, saved in **(A)** were considered relevant for building the Amazonia case study.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.10_07-2021_(A)	pdf	187 KB	List of 120 references used to inform the Amazonia case study.